

Enhancing Bank Credit Risk Management Using the C5.0 Decision Tree Algorithm

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Abstract: This paper discusses the relationship between financial fraud risk and credit risk in China's financial market, and points out that financial statement fraud has a serious impact on the fairness and transparency of the capital market, and damages the legitimate rights and interests of investors. Research shows that financial fraud risk may be an important signal of credit risk outbreak, and may further spread through the credit network, resulting in a larger scale of credit risk. This paper reviews the evolution of credit risk assessment models, from early expert analysis methods to modern statistical and machine learning-based methods, including Z-score models, SVM models, and random forests. Special attention is paid to the application of the C5.0 algorithm in credit risk assessment, highlighting its advantages in terms of data characteristics and prediction accuracy. Finally, the ROC curve and KS curve are used to evaluate the prediction effect of the model, which shows that the model has good prediction ability and practical value, and provides a new methodology for financial fraud risk assessment.

Keywords: Financial Fraud Risk , Credit Risk Assessment , Machine Learning , C5.0 Algorithm.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In addition to credit risk, financial fraud risk is also a prominent problem in China's financial market. Financial Statement Fraud (or Accounting Fraud) referred to in this paper refers to "a deliberate and illegal act committed by a listed company to cause damage and injury to investors and creditors through the use of materially misleading financial statements". The financial fraud of listed companies has seriously damaged the fairness and transparency of the capital market, damaged the legitimate rights and interests of the majority of investors, and is also the key object of supervision and law enforcement of China Securities Regulatory Commission. There is an organic relationship between financial fraud risk and credit risk.[1-3]Financial fraud risk indicates that enterprises have significant financial difficulties, which may be an important signal of the outbreak of credit risk, and financial fraud risk can further spread through the credit network, resulting in a larger scale of credit risk. He Yunfu's research found that commercial banks' credit risk assessment of enterprises is mostly based on financial information. Taking the credit assessment of enterprise groups as an example, when financial information is

incomplete, lag and false, the accuracy of credit risk assessment will have insurmountable defects. That is, when there is fraud in financial statements, the credit risk assessment is likely to fail. It is found that financial crisis caused by financial fraud risk may be the root cause of credit risk and an important part of credit risk. Credit risk is the accumulation and extension of financial crisis caused by financial fraud risk. The identification of financial fraud risk may be an important signal before the outbreak of credit risk. It is found that enterprise default may spread to affiliated enterprises through specific financial connections, and the financial distress of enterprises may be amplified through supplier-customer commercial credit relationship, bank-enterprise credit relationship, and guarantee relationship between production enterprises. [4]The financial distress of enterprises not only affects themselves, but also has a significant impact on the credit risk of upstream suppliers. Based on the perspective of supply chain, this paper examines the risk transmission effect.

The research on credit risk assessment models has a long history, and many models have been derived. The earliest credit risk assessment model is the expert analysis method, which relies on experienced credit experts to conduct

a comprehensive analysis based on various factors of the applicant, including "5C", "5P", "5W", etc. However, this method mainly relies on the subjective score of experts, mainly qualitative analysis, and there are certain limitations in the scope of application. Subsequently, a series of landmark studies created a system of credit risk modeling methods, such as Z-score model and ZETA model (Altman et al.), which laid the foundation for research on credit risk assessment models based on quantitative analysis. The introduction of post-linear discriminant analysis (Altman, 1968[5]) Logistic model (Wiginton, Martin, 1977 and other statistical methods further improved the effectiveness of credit risk assessment model construction[5].

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 CREDIT RISK RELATED RESEARCH

According to the Basel II Accord, credit risk refers to the loss caused by the decline of asset prices in the portfolio due to changes in the credit level and performance ability of the trading object. Furthermore, many scholars at home and abroad have put forward different theories on credit risk assessment.

the earliest theory of credit risk assessment was published in 1776 in An inquiry into the nature and causes of ofthe wealth of Nations B6. The famous economist Adam Smith proposed the Commercial credit Theory ("commercial-Loan theory"), also known as the "Real bill Theory". In 1919, Harold Glenn Moulton further proposed the "Shiftability Theory" in Commercial Banking and Capital Formation:ACriticism. In 1949, Herbert V. Prochow proposed the "Anticipated Income Theory ofLiquidity" of loan liquidity [6-7], and the research of these early scholars laid the foundation for subsequent credit risk assessment theories. Since the 1930s, research on credit risk assessment and management has gradually begun to explore in depth, and in the 1960s, relevant research showed a trend of intense intensity. However, the previous research mainly focused on qualitative analysis, supplemented by some statistical methods, and then modern credit risk assessment and management methods gradually emerged.

The earliest credit risk assessment model is expert analysis. This method is based on the comprehensive analysis of different factors of the applicant by experienced credit experts, and finally make credit decisions through subjective judgment. This method is limited by the lack of historical sample data in the early stage of banking institutions, which cannot be judged by data mining methods. [8]Expert analysis methods include "5C", "5P", "5W" and so on. "5C" refers to the applicant's Character, Collateral, Capacity, Capital and Cycle Condition, respectively. The "5Ps" respectively refer to Personal(personal characteristics), Purpose(purpose), Payment(repayment factors), Protection(repayment guarantee), and Perspective(debt repayment prospects). "5W" respectively refers to Who(applicant), Why(purpose of loan),

When(repayment period), What(security), HoW(solvency). Although the above methods describe the applicant's borrowing and repayment behavior slightly different, but still in the applicant's personal characteristics, solvency, guarantee, repayment period, external environment and other major factors. [9]Expert analysis can be implemented easily in credit practice, but its disadvantages are obvious. Different credit experts cannot guarantee the consistency and objectivity of evaluation standards, and the standards of bank credit risk control are highly dependent on individual experts and cannot be large-scale business. With the accumulation of bank credit sample data, quantitative analysis methods based on statistical methods have become popular.

The early Z-score model and ZETA model were preliminary explorations. Altman(1968)P proposed the Z.Core model. The model takes bankrupt and non-bankrupt companies in the United States as a sample set, and adopts 22 applicants' financial characteristics and solvency characteristics. Subsequently, Altman et al. (1977)[0 further extended the ZETA model and expanded the five variables in the original model to seven variables, greatly improving the effectiveness of the model. Altman et al. (1981) applied the improved ZETA model to commercial purposes. Then KMV, CreditRisk+, Credit Portfolio View and other business models gradually emerged, among which KMV company proposed the KMV model based on Merton option pricing theory in 1993. By calculating the Default Distance DD(Default Distance) of loan applicants, the model further obtains the mapping relationship between DD and Expected default frequency EDF(Expected DefaultFrequency) based on the database, and synthesizes a smooth curve to estimate the value of EDF[10-12]. Credit Suisse proposed the CreditRisk+ model in 1996, which applied the actuarial method in insurance to calculate the loss distribution of the loan Portfolio and could effectively predict whether the loan applicant would default.

In addition, the Logistic model has been widely recognized. Martin(1977)used Logistie function to predict the bankruptcy and default probability of a company, and found that the prediction effect of Logistic model was better than that of Z-score model and ZETA model. On this basis, Press and Wilson(1978) and Sjur and Wijst(2001)[41 constructed the Probit model with the Logistic function. Fang Hongquan and Zeng Yong (2004)[42] based on Logit model and linear discrimination model, and taking financial data as an indicator, verified that the two models have strong forecasting ability for credit risk.

The credit risk identification model based on statistical method has been widely used in the practice of commercial banks and has supported the credit risk management business of commercial banks for a long time.

2.2 CREDIT DEFAULT PREDICTION MODEL BASED ON SVM MACHINE LEARNING

With the accumulation of large amounts of data and the

rapid development of machine learning technology, the research of credit risk recognition model based on machine learning has become the research direction of many scholars.

Neural network models are the origin of machine learning techniques. [13]West(2000) Constructed a credit scoring model by using five neural network models of "multi-layer perceptron mixed expert, radial basis function, learning vector quantization and fuzzy adaptive resonance", and compared it with linear discriminant analysis, Logistic regression, K-nearest neighbor, kernel density estimation, decision tree and other methods on two sample sets. The results show that the traditional Logistic model has a better effect, while the neural network model, multi-layer perceptron may not have a good effect, and the hybrid expert and radial basis function neural network models have a good effect and can be considered for application in practice.

Then, SVM(Support vector Machine) method was proposed to further expand the method system of credit risk assessment model construction[14-18]. Huang et al. (2004) Using SVM, backpropagation neural network (BNN) and other methods, taking the US and Taiwan markets as sample sets, found that the prediction accuracy of these two methods was about 80%, and further studied how to improve the explainability of the model. MinandLee(2005)[9] Construct credit risk assessment model with SVM. It is combined with Multiple Discriminant Analysis (MDA), logistic regression analysis (Logit), and three-layer fully connected backpropagation neural networks (Back PropagationNeuralNetwork, BPN) method were compared, the results show that the SVM model has better prediction accuracy. [19]Then the SVM (support vector machine) approach is put forward to further expanding the method system of credit risk assessment model building. Huang et al. (2004) Using SVM, backpropagation neural network (BNN) and other methods, taking the US and Taiwan markets as sample sets, found that the prediction accuracy of these two methods was about 80%, and further studied how to improve the explainability of the model. MinandLee(2005) Construct credit risk assessment model with SVM[20]. And Multiple Discriminant Analysis , MDA), logistic regression analysis (Logit) and connect all three layer back propagation neural network (BPN) BackPropagationNeuralNetwork, methods are compared, and the research results show that the SVM model has better prediction accuracy. In addition, some scholars improved the SVM method and proposed a new credit risk assessment model. [21]Huang et al. (2007)used three strategies to build a credit scoring model based on hybrid support vector machine, and verified it with two credit risk datasets in UCI database. Compared with neural network, genetic algorithm and decision tree,SVM can obtain similar prediction accuracy with fewer input features. Luo et al. (2020) Based on SVM, an improved QSSVM model was proposed, which has better prediction accuracy compared with traditional SVM and other methods. In addition to SVM algorithm, the research of credit risk assessment model based on decision tree algorithm has also made important

progress[22-24]. Lee et al. (2006)proposed Classification&Regression TreeCART and Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines, The results show that the prediction effectiveness of the above two methods is higher than that of traditional discriminant analysis, Logistic regression, neural network and support vector machine. Nie et al. (2011)Based on Chinese data, this paper constructs a credit risk identification model based on Logistic regression and decision tree, considering economic significance and correlation selection features from customer information, card information, risk information and transaction activity information. The predictive effectiveness of Logistic regression algorithm is better than decision tree algorithm.

2.3 RANDOM FOREST (RF)

Breiman(1996)[92] first proposed Bagging strategy. On the basis of the original paper, the author further proposed the random forest algorithm by introducing random feature sampling (Breiman,2001).

Bagging strategy is a typical parallel mechanism that combines different submodels by self-sampling. For example, given a data set with N samples $Z_1 = [z_1, z_2, \dots, z_i, \dots, z_N]$, ie{1,2,... , N}, obtain a new dataset Z with N samples through N times of random sampling with replacement, M times of repeated sampling can obtain M sample sets $Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_m$. Based on $Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_m$ trained the model 22 times to obtain M weak classifiers, and finally combined M weak classifiers to form the final strong classification through parallel mechanism[25-27].

FIGURE 1. SCHEMATIC DIAGRAM OF DECISION TREE STRATEGY

As shown in the figure. Random forest algorithm further randomly samples features based on Bagging strategy. Assuming that a certain sample set has X features, random forest algorithm only classifies each weak classifier into x features (meeting $x \ll X$) during sampling, and increases the number of weak classifiers. The idea is to "form a forest of decision trees generated by a large number of random samples". [28]This algorithm can greatly reduce the dimensional disaster problem and prevent the overfitting problem in the single decision tree model. This paper believes

that it can be well applied to the financial fraud risk assessment data set.

3 METHODOLOGY

In simple terms, for a dataset, we set up the first classifier through some algorithm, if the first classifier is good for the classification of samples x_1, x_2 , but poor for x_3 , then the second classifier increases the weight of x_3 through a magic formula, and reduces the weight of x_1, x_2 . Why is that? Because we think that the first classifier can already classify x_1 and x_2 well, but not x_3 , we do not need to let the second classifier consider x_1 and x_2 , because we have the first class to deal with them, so the second classifier is to complement the first classifier, so that it can consider more data that the first classifier can not accurately classify[29-31]. And then you put together a bunch of these classifiers, and each classifier can generally classify some data and some data that they can't classify, but they use their gay friends to help them classify the data that they can't, and finally they all integrate together to form a super powerful classifier. Finally, give each classifier a weight to see how important they are in the big classifier, the general formula is $H(x)=\text{sign}(\text{sum}(\text{weight} * \text{classifier } t))$, $t=1,2,\dots,N$ means that the output of all classifiers is added up, and the sign is taken to get the final result.

3.1 C5.0 FUNCTION ALGORITHM MODEL

The C5.0 function makes it easy to add the Adaboost algorithm to the C5.0 decision tree. We just need to add an additional parameter trials that represents the number of independent decision trees used in the model enhancement team. The trials parameter sets an upper limit, and if the algorithm identifies additional trials that don't seem to improve the model's accuracy, it will stop adding decision trees. Brett Lantz, in his book Machine Learning and the R Language, states that the C5.0 algorithm is suitable for most types of problems and can be used directly. Compared to other advanced machine learning models (neural networks and SVMs)[32], decision trees built with C5.0 algorithms generally perform almost as well as other advanced models and are easier to understand and deploy.

One of the advantages of the C5.0 algorithm is that it can be automatically pruned, that is, it pays attention to many decisions and can automatically use fairly reasonable defaults. The overall strategy of the algorithm is to prune the decision tree after the fact, which generates a large decision tree that overfits the training data, and then deletes the nodes and branches that have little effect on the classification error.

3.2 DATA CHARACTERISTICS

`C5.0Control(subset = TRUE, bands = 0, winnow = FALSE, noGlobalPruning = FALSE, CF = 0.25, minCases = 2, fuzzyThreshold = FALSE, sample = 0, seed = sample.int(4096, size = 1) - 1L, earlyStopping = TRUE, label = "outcome")`

FIGURE 2. SCHEMATIC DIAGRAM OF C5.0 SYNTAX STRUCTURE

Combining true positive and true negative in the confusion matrix, it can be seen that C5.0 algorithm has the highest accuracy in this data set. Of course, we only make a simple comparison. For example, pruning operations have not been carried out in ID3 and CART algorithms.

3.3 EXPERIMENTAL CONCLUSION

The decision tree model shows the following result for a parameter with a maximum depth of 3, the hit ratio (TPR) = 34%. The prediction accuracy of the model as a whole reached 83%. For binary classification problem, ROC curve and KS curve are ideal model evaluation methods. [33-34] This paper uses these two graphs to evaluate the structure of the model. According to the position of the ROC curve, the prediction accuracy can be judged. The closer the curve is to the top left corner (smaller X, larger Y), the higher the prediction accuracy. Area under the ROC curve (AUC). The larger the AUC value, the higher the prediction accuracy. The ROC curve of the model is steep, close to the upper left corner of (0,1), and the AOC value reaches 90.18%, which indicates that the prediction accuracy of the model is high. KS curve, with hit rate and false alarm rate as the vertical axis and threshold as the horizontal axis, is a tool used to measure the performance of classification models, and can well measure the relationship between hit rate and false alarm rate. As shown below, as the threshold increases, the false alarm rate decreases; The hit rate remains unchanged until 0.4892, and when the threshold is exceeded, when the threshold is close to 0.4892, the hit rate begins to decline rapidly. Therefore, the maximum KS value is 79.09% at 0.4892. If the KS curve is close to the horizontal axis, the performance of the classifier is poor. If the curve is close to the vertical axis, the performance of the classifier is better. As can be seen from the figure, the performance of this model is at a good level.

4 CONCLUSION

This paper deeply discusses the close relationship between financial fraud risk and credit risk, and emphasizes the key role of the former in the evaluation of the latter. Research shows that financial fraud not only damages the transparency and fairness of the market, but also may become an important precursor to the outbreak of credit risk. Therefore, early identification of financial fraud risk is of great significance to reduce the potential credit crisis.

By using C5.0 decision tree algorithm, this paper demonstrates the effective application of machine learning technology in financial fraud risk assessment. The model's high predictive accuracy and good performance, as shown by the ROC curve and KS curve, suggest that modern technology can significantly enhance the practicality and reliability of credit risk assessment. This provides a powerful tool for financial institutions to identify and respond to potential risks in a timely manner when developing risk management strategies.

Going forward, research can be further expanded to integrate and optimize multiple machine learning models and explore synergies between different algorithms to improve the comprehensiveness and accuracy of credit risk assessment. At the same time, combined with big data technology, the potential risk signals in enterprise financial data can be more deeply mined, and the development of intelligent risk management can be promoted. In addition, customized risk assessment models for industry-specific risk characteristics will also become an important direction of future research. These efforts will help build a more sound financial system and ensure the long-term stability and development of the market.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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